

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Том 2, Выпуск 2, 29 Февраль

IXTHIOSIS DISEASE CLINICAL SYMPTOMS, DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT METHODS

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Abstract: Study of ichthyosis disease and its forms, diagnostics and modern treatment methods.

Key words: ichthyosis, vulgar and congenital ichthyosis, xeroderma, simple and shiny ichthyosis, symptomatic therapy, vitamin therapy, hormonal therapy, physiotherapy.

Ichthyosis is a hereditary skin disease in which the skin becomes dry and flaky, with thick crusty layers resembling fish scales. Symptoms of ichthyosis appear in early childhood, become evident in adulthood and last until the end of life. It is noted that the disease is transmitted from generation to generation in autosomal dominant and autosomal recessive forms. Autosomal-recessive form of ichthyosis is distinguished by its severe course, poor response to treatment measures, and complications. There are 2 forms of ichthyosis: vulgar ichthyosis and congenital ichthyosis. Congenital ichthyosis, in turn, includes types of epidermolytic Brock's ichthyotic dry erythroderma and lamellar ichthyosis. Vulgar ichthyosis (ichthyosis vulgaris) has an autosomal-dominant form of reproduction, symptoms of the disease appear in the 1st-4th years of children's life and develop maximally during the period up to 10 years of age, and continue until the end of the patient's life. The disease is mild in the summer months of the year, and the course of the disease is much better when the sick children reach adulthood. The process is

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characterized by a diffused appearance of skin dryness, thickening (hyperkeratosis), and follicular keratosis. This condition leads to a significant decrease in the function of sweat and sebaceous glands and to the complete cessation of these glands. The disease is mainly located in the writing areas of the hands and feet (especially in the area of the elbow and knee joints), wrists, waist, buttocks. In childhood, the process is also observed in the areas of the skin of the face and forehead, and later these areas are cleared of acne. Buttocks and groin areas, armpits, groin folds, and genitals are usually not affected. Symptoms of ichthyosis vulgaris are the size of a coin and can range from small, thin, white flakes to thick, large dark patches. Vulgar ichthyosis disease is classified as follows (according to the degree of dryness of the skin, the type and accumulation of scaly plaques or scales): 1. Xeroderma (xeroderma) is a mild type of ichthyosis, in which the skin is dry and scaly. 2. Simple ichthyosis (ichthyosis simplex) - is characterized by thick, dry, hard and non-smooth plate-like scales closely adhering to the skin. 3. Shiny ichthyosis (ichthyosis mtida) - is characterized by a large amount of keratin masses on the legs and arms, at the mouth of hair follicles. The flakes will have a unique pearl color and shine. Sometimes the rash is linear and looks like snake skin. These scales thicken and freeze again, have a dark-gray color and form a deep depression (serpentine ichthyosis - serpentina). And finally, the most severe form of ichthyosis hystrix (hystrix - jayra) - in which in the limited areas of the skin, especially in the writing areas of the legs and hands, thick aggregates of icterosis appear spiky, 5-10 mm above the skin level. it rises and resembles the thorns of the jaira. The process is followed by drying, thinning and thinning of hair and hair, thickening, thinning or increased brittleness of nail plates.

Treatment

The treatment of ichthyosis is carried out comprehensively, taking into account the age of the patient, the clinical form of the disease, and the degree of severity. In particular, Ayevit medicine is given to sick children up to 6 months of age, 1 drop with milk, 1 time a day; Children 7-12 months 1 drop per day every day; 1-3-year-old children are exempted; 1 capsule daily for 3-6 year olds; 6-14 years old 1 capsule daily for 20 days. Ascorbic acid up to 6 months - 0.025-0.05 times 3 times/day; 0.05-0.075 mg x 3 times/day for children aged 7-12 months; 1-6 years old - 0.075-0.1 mg x 3 times/day; 7-14 years old - 0.1-0.15 x 3 times/day; Riboflavin mononucleotide 1% solution up to 6 months - 0.2 ml intramuscularly, 7-12 months -0.3 ml; 4-6 years old - 0.5-0.7 ml; 7-14 years old - 0.8-1.0 ml. Nicotinic acid 1% solution up to 6 months - 0.1-0.2 ml; 4-12 months -0.2-0.3 ml; 1-3 years old - 0.5-0.4 ml; 4-6 years old - 0.5-0.5 ml; 7-14 years old - 1 ml. Trental oral tablet 10 ml - 2-3 times/day after meals; 1/3-1/2 tab in children under 1 year; Adults from 1 year

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old - 1 tab 2-3 times/day for 1 month. Methionine 0.1 g up to 1 year; 2 years old-0.2 g; From 3 to 4 years - from 0.25 g; From 5 to 6 years - up to 0.3 g; 7 years and older 0.5 g 3 times/day 30 minutes before meals. The course of treatment is carried out for 10 days, then rest and the course of treatment is returned. Solcoseryl (Actovegin) up to 1 year old - 1-2 ml intramuscularly/between; 1-14 years - 2 ml intravenously. For local application: 2% salicylic ointment and lanolin cream are applied together with ayevit (per gram: 1 drop).

Conclusion: The investigations showed that ichthyosis is a hereditary skin disease in which the keratinization process is disturbed. Dry skin crusts, and in severe cases of the disease, scars appear on it. Often, ichthyosis manifests itself in early childhood. Its acquired form is very rare. As a rule, ichthyosis has a clear clinical picture and does not cause any difficulties in diagnosis. Additional examination methods include: histological analysis of the skin; general and biochemical blood tests; general analysis of urine. Unfortunately, ichthyosis cannot be completely cured. Modern medicine can only reduce the symptoms. Drug therapy is indicated for this: vitamins A, B, C, E and niacin complexes; hormonal drugs to improve the functioning of the thyroid gland. Local medications and physical therapy are necessary. Ointments and creams are prescribed to moisturize the skin. Salicylic acid relieves inflammation and disinfects the skin. As physiotherapeutic treatments, medicated baths and mud are prescribed, which heal the skin and relieve itching. The active agent is selected by the doctor depending on the type of ichthyosis.

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